

SPORT IS THE GUARANTEE OF A HEALTHY LIFE

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ABSTRACT

This article contains information about the fact that engaging in sports, physical education, and maintaining a healthy lifestyle is a guarantee of health. It is worth noting that the second direction of the five important initiatives put forward by the head of our state - physical training of young people and creation of necessary conditions for them to show their abilities in the field of sports, paves the way for mass sports events in the coming years.

Introduction. Sport is beauty, elegance, courage, strength and, most importantly, health. A person who regularly practices sports always feels refreshed and relaxed. Regular sports activities ensure the active functioning of the human body. Because as a result of training loads, blood circulation is activated due to the increase in the minute volume of the heart. As a result of the active movement of blood circulation at high pressure, the process of metabolism is also activated. This in itself ensures the physiological, anatomical and functional stability of the human body.

We all know that sport is a guarantee of health. Therefore, sports are becoming popular in Uzbekistan. The fact that the number of our compatriots who follow a healthy lifestyle is increasing day by day is proof of our opinion.

The Decree of the President Sh. Mirziyoyev dated October 30, 2020 "On measures for the wide implementation of a healthy lifestyle and further development of mass sports" gave a new spirit to our actions in this regard. No matter what season it is, we meet a lot of people jogging in the streets early in the morning.

It is worth noting that the second direction of the five important initiatives put forward by the head of our state - physical training of young people and creation of necessary conditions for them to show their abilities in the field of sports, paves the way for mass sports events in the coming years.

The main part. One of the main tasks of today is to promote a healthy lifestyle among the population and young people, to form their desire for a healthy lifestyle, to meaningfully organize their free time, to increase their interest in sports, and to attract them to sports clubs. It is an obvious fact for all of us that a healthy lifestyle is a guarantee of human health and longevity, and it is an expression of a healthy lifestyle and a prosperous life of the population.

Laziness leads to disorder and diseases (Abu Raykhan Beruni). Sport has always played an important role in human life. There is information that some types of sports existed in ancient Egypt 4 thousand years ago. In the ancient East, serious attention was paid to women becoming well-educated and strong. The head of every state must be a leading general. Amir Temur, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur, who left an indelible mark in history, were such rulers.

The main measure of health care is physical education. A person who exercises regularly and regularly does not get sick. Physical education increases innate heat and gives relief to the body. Because it easily generates heat and removes waste products accumulated in the body. As for the types of physical education, they are as follows: performing various exercises with light movements, archery, fast walking, javelin throwing, hanging, jumping on one leg, shaking both hands, during which a person stands on tiptoes, hands in front of him and moves backwards. These are quick actions. A body builder should first rub the body with a hard cloth to prepare the body.

According to research, in the majority of pedagogical works created by our enlightened ancestors in the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, special attention was paid to raising a child physically healthy.

In particular, in this regard, Abdurauf Fitrat's views on the issues of organizing physical education on the basis of social education and raising a person to be healthy and strong are worthy of attention. In the chapter entitled "Child Education" of his work "Rahbari Najot" it is said: "Physical education has been given great importance since ancient times. If all parts of a person are not healthy and strong, then a person will not live long. If one of the parts of a person's body is affected by halal, that person will withdraw from work and become a needy person."

Everyone tries to be healthy, fresh and energetic, to keep their youth, beauty and ability to work. One of the main factors to achieve this is physical activity.

Deciding on a healthy lifestyle in our society has risen to the level of state policy, and at the same time, fundamental reforms in raising a physically mature and healthy generation are being gradually implemented in our country. For example, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Physical Education and Sports" and the Cabinet of Ministers' Decision "On Measures for the Further Development of Physical Education and Sports in Uzbekistan" The important tasks that have been carried out have been expressed.

Of course, it is not necessary for everyone to be a highly qualified athlete, to participate in competitions and receive awards. However, it is beneficial for a person to regularly play sports and exercise according to his ability. Or 15-20 minutes of morning exercise, 40-60 minutes of walking in the open air, 20-30 minutes of walking before going to bed, which can be done every day, will definitely make such wishes come true.

Modern medicine shows the existence of conditions such as a decrease in the level of health of a person due to a lack of physical activity, a violation of the functioning of internal organs, a low indicator of work ability, and physical development that is not at the level of demand. After all, this is the reason for the opinion of ancient philosophers that the thing that makes a person unconscious and harms his health is not doing physical activity for a long time.

If the teaching of the great Hakim Abu Ali ibn Sina: "Badantarbiya is a glorious way to maintain health" becomes the life motto of every person, then a person will never get sick.

Physical education and sports allow the growing generation to become adults, and at the same time, it allows them to make good use of their free time. The human body develops in harmony with the external environment. This harmony, as well as the activity of all organs, is controlled by the central nervous system. Regular, uninterrupted physical activity has a good effect on human health: metabolism improves, body tissues absorb nutrients better, and decomposed substances leave the body faster.

People of all ages can engage in morning physical education classes. The exercises will give positive results only if they are performed continuously. A long-term break can lead to a decrease in the effect of previous training.

In fact, energy is needed for movement, and energy is obtained by processing food products, fats and carbohydrates. Movement helps improve breathing, blood vessels, digestion, and blood production systems.

For this reason, people who are physically active are light, refreshed, full of energy, their speech is clear, their mood is high and stable. As a result of performing physical exercises, the body's defense system develops well. Here, the result of a study conducted by physiologists-scientists with the participation of more than 200 people can be cited as an example. According to this study, which was conducted in order to determine the level of emotions of people who are constantly and consistently engaged in physical exercises, 72% of those who took part in the experiment consider themselves to be very happy. As the reason for this, they note that they are constantly engaged in physical exercises.

Exercises starting from childhood and adolescence are especially useful. Everyone needs to train their body to a stable regime. Engaging in physical education, outdoor activities, and sports are among the factors that ensure longevity and health.

In addition, in our relatively hot climate, it is advisable to train the body with non-traditional methods. In particular, exercise methods such as various foot baths, walking on salt and stone paths, as well as walking in the open air before and after sleep, strengthen the body's immune system.

In a word, health is a person's mental calmness and ability to resist the harmful effects of the external environment. And exercise is considered a mechanism of gradual adaptation of the organism under the influence of water, sun and air. In order to live a healthy life, it is necessary to train the body in various natural environmental conditions. It is necessary to inculcate this especially in the minds of our youth. After all, training from childhood and adolescence is a guarantee of a healthy life and a long life.

The more our daily sports loads are, the same loads will slowly show their effect on our internal functional state. Now our internal members are also training with us. As a result of regular training and an increase in the volume of general loads, we can see positive conditions such as the strengthening of the muscles of the heart wall, the expansion of the coronary arteries, and the increase of the vital capacity of the lungs.

What if the situation is reversed? Negative conditions such as inactivity, improper diet, and bad habits are the biggest enemies of human health. Movement is the basis of human activity. Management in the system of actions is inextricably linked with knowledge of its

structure. Studying the structure of movements and their control allows us to use the laws of movement in human movement activity.

Speaking about the laws of motion, we found it necessary to mention the effects of the physicist Isaac Newton's laws of mechanics. Newton's first law is the law of inertia. A body remains at rest until it is acted upon by an external force. A moving object continues to move at a constant speed and direction until another external force acts on it.

Newton's second law is the law of acceleration. When a force acts on an object, an acceleration proportional to the force is created and causes a change in motion. Force = weight + acceleration Newton's third law is the law of opposite forces. Every action of a force causes a counter-reaction - a counter-action of equal magnitude and opposite direction. With these laws of Newton, human movement can be justified. The human movement apparatus consists of more than 206 bones and more than 600 muscles, and is part of the movement system in the body.

Conclusion. In conclusion, I found it permissible to quote the words of Perde Couberton, the founder of the modern Olympic Games: "Run if you want to be beautiful, run if you want to be healthy, run if you want to be rich!" Because our health is our greatest wealth.

Therefore, anyone who wants to live a long life on the basis of training his body, increasing labor productivity, strengthening health, should always engage in physical education, as well as conduct his daily activities based on a certain order.

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